

Stearic Acid Functionality in Water Evaporation Suppression

Ali Mozafari, Undergraduate Student
School of Mechanical Engineering
University of Tehran
Tehran, Iran
Mozafari.ali@hotmail.com

Bozorgmehr Mansouri, Undergraduate Student
School of Mechanical Engineering
University of Tehran
Tehran, Iran
Bozorgmehr_mansouri@hotmail.com

Abstract— Water scarcity is now a major crisis in many parts of the world and is beginning to emerge as a serious problem for many other nations. Therefore, there has been a lot of efforts put to confine water waste in recent years. For instance, a significant amount of water is yearly evaporated from water reservoirs such as dams, all around the world. In this paper, a method is presented, which is using Stearic acid and Calcium Carbonate to form a monolayer on water surface, to restrict evaporation from bodies of water. Experimentations are conducted to assess the functionality of the Stearic acid. Also, optimal amount of the chemical and the best method for it to be applied to water surface are identified. Performance of Stearic acid is also evaluated while air flows above water surface by experiment. It is confirmed that Stearic acid, has proper functionality and therefore could be used to save water from evaporation in water reservoirs.

Keywords-water scarcity; monolayers; evaporation suppression; long-chain fatty acids.

I. INTRODUCTION

If we take a quick glance to photographs of Earth, we can readily understand that our planet may encounter hard water crisis in next decades. According to geological surveys, much of the fresh water on earth is inaccessible and less than one-third of this water is found on ground-waters such as lakes, swamps and rivers. Also, with the rapid growth of population beside dramatic changes in the climate of Earth, the problem of scarcity of ground-water becomes much more significant than the past. With these regretfully

facts about few sources of water on our planet, wise utilization and recognition of its loss factor seem necessary. One of these factors is evaporation from water surfaces in reservoirs. This loss can be as much as 40% of total water stored behind a dam. In Texas, long-term mean evaporation from many reservoirs in the Texas water rights permit system is estimated to be 7.53 billion m^2 /year [1]. Thus, lots of attention should be paid for reducing evaporation from large bodies of water. Several methods have been carried out to restrict water evaporation, including wind breaks, physical and chemical barriers. Hunter did a massive project by covering East Gippsland water at bemm river by shade-cloth and reduced amount of heat entering the surface of water in addition to minimizing airborne contamination [2]. Beside utilizing physical barriers, using chemicals has also become prevalent. It has been known for a long time that monomolecular films of certain non-poisonous alcohols can suppress water evaporation. Rideal was the first researcher who found that monolayers could be used to reduce water evaporation [3]. This seems to be the only viable technology for reducing the evaporative losses of water from reservoirs [4]. Subsequently, Langmuir and Schaefer made the first quantitative experiments on the monolayers and found the temperature dependence of the evaporation resistance to permeation by evaporating water molecules [5]. In 2005, Gugliotti et al. used the ability of monomolecular films of fatty alcohols in order to decrease the rate of evaporation from two natural sources in São Paulo by mixed films of hexadecanol and octadecanol [6]. In confirmation of Gugliotti's

experiments, in 2008, Barnes showed that the principal compounds that have been shown to be effective in monomolecular layers are hexadecanol and octadecanol [7]. For gaining profound vision of the performance of monolayers, in 2008 Cook et al. did lots of experiments in different locations and found that the amount of evaporation from sources of water depends on parameters such as temperature of water, speed of wind and contamination and generated one specific model for water evaporation [8]. Among recent works on the monolayers and their effectiveness, it is worth to mention the use of soluble surfactants, which showed little influence on evaporation reduction [9]. Other works have focused attention on the influence of mixed films on evaporation reduction and showed that the evaporation resistance of fatty alcohols can be strengthened by adding suitable chemicals [10].

In this paper, Stearic acid (which is a long-chain fatty acid) mixed with Calcium Carbonate is used in order to suppress water evaporation. Experiments are conducted in order to find the efficiency of this acid, optimum amount of this chemical to be dispersed on water's surface in order to reach maximum efficiency, the best method to apply this material on water's surface and its resistance to wind flow above the surface of water.

II. EXPERIMENTATION AND TEST SETUP

The powder used in experiments conducted in this paper is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. The powder used in experiments

In this paper, experiments are conducted in three steps. In the first step, eight vessels, only one of which contain pure water, are tested during a twenty four-hour period. Other vessels contain different amounts of powder. Through this step, optimum amount of powder to reach

the maximum efficiency and the maximum efficiency in evaporation suppression itself, are identified simultaneously.

In the second step, most suitable method to disperse the powder on water's surface is identified. Three vessels containing a same amount of water, but powder is dispersed on their surfaces by different methods are observed during a day. Vessel No.1 contains solid powder, vessel No.2 contains powder mixed with water and vessel No.3 contains powder mixed with an organic solvent.

In the third step, one vessel containing water and optimum amount of powder is placed in front of a wind tunnel (Fig. 2) for thirteen days. For each day a different wind velocity is set for the wind tunnel. Water height in vessel is observed during the day. Also, the water and powder dispersed on its surface is emptied and freshened for the next day.

Figure 2. The wind tunnel used in last stage of experiment

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results from our experiments are presented. Figure 3 shows the results of the first step of experiments.

Figure 3. Efficiency of the powder for different amounts per area

According to Figure 3, it is clear that the amount of saved water increases if more powder is dispersed on the surface of water, but if the amount of powder exceeds 0.06 grams per square meter, the efficiency does not change significantly. So, 0.06 g/m² of powder could be considered as the optimum amount of powder to be dispersed on the surface of water in order to obtain maximum economically feasible efficiency, which is 24%.

Figure 4 shows the performance of powder applied to the surface of water in three different methods.

Figure 4. Performance of the powder applied in three methods

As it is comprehended from this chart, solid powder performs better than powder mixed with water or solvent. Figure 5 displays the performance of the powder while wind flow is passing above the surface of water.

Figure 5. Efficiency of the powder at different wind speeds passing above the surface.

Functionality of the powder decreases significantly when wind flows faster above the surface until at approximately 21 km/h when the powder is not functional at all.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper a new method was presented in order to restrict water evaporation from reservoirs by using a

mixture of Stearic acid and Calcium Carbonate. Experiments are conducted in order to prove the functionality of this chemical. On the first step of our experiment, it was understood that 0.06 grams per unit area of chemical is the optimum amount to reach a cost-effective quantity of material to be used. This optimum amount results to approximately 24% percent of saved water from evaporation. On the second stage of our experiment it was concluded that this chemical must be applied to the surface of water in solid state, not solved in solvent or mixed with water. From the last stage of experiment, it was understood that this material is still functional until 21 km/h wind is passing above the surface of water, at which the powder loses its functionality.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wurbs, R. A., & Ayala, R. A. (2014). Reservoir evaporation in Texas, USA. *Journal of Hydrology*, 510, 1-9.
- [2] Solutions, N. W., & Verlee, D. (2006). Evaporation mitigation technology (EMT) manufacturers liaison report.
- [3] Rideal, E. K. (1925). On the influence of thin surface films on the evaporation of water. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 29(12), 1585-1588.
- [4] La Mer, V. K., & Healy, T. W. (1965). Evaporation of Water: Its Retardation by Monolayers Spreading a monomolecular film on the surface is a tested and economical means of reducing water loss. *Science*, 148(3666), 36-42.
- [5] Langmuir, I., & Schaefer, V. J. (1943). Rates of evaporation of water through compressed monolayers on water. *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, 235(2), 119-162.
- [6] Gugliotti, M., Baptista, M. S., & Politi, M. J. (2005). Reduction of evaporation of natural water samples by monomolecular films. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 16(6A), 1186-1190.
- [7] Barnes, G. T. (2008). The potential for monolayers to reduce the evaporation of water from large water storages. *Agricultural Water Management*, 95(4), 339-353.
- [8] Cook, F., Knight, J., & Burn, S. (2008). Evaporation reduction by monolayers: overview, modelling and effectiveness. *Urban Water Security Research Alliance*.
- [9] Lunkenheimer, K., & Zembala, M. (1997). Attempts to study a water evaporation retardation by soluble surfactants. *Journal of colloid and interface science*, 188(2), 363-371.
- [10] McNamee, C. E., Barnes, G. T., Gentle, I. R., Peng, J. B., Steitz, R., & Probert, R. (1998). The evaporation resistance of mixed monolayers of octadecanol and cholesterol. *Journal of colloid and interface science*, 207(2), 258-263.